

Chemical physics of non-covalent interaction between tetraphenylporphyrin and (dibenzoylmethanato)borondifluoride in methylene chloride

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Abstract : The most active core pyrrolic protons of free base tetraphenylporphyrin (P1-P3) participate in non-covalent interaction with (dibenzoylmethanato)borondifluoride (MBDF1) in methylene chloride medium. The chemical physics of the well established reaction equilibrium was studied both in the ground as well as in excited state. The spectroscopic observation of isobestic and isoemissive formation were justified on the basis of Mulliken charge distribution, frontier molecular orbital interaction as well as DFT optimized H-bonded molecular assemblies studied theoretically through calculation of NBO based bond index calculations.

Keywords : Free base tetraphenylporphyrin, haloboranes, non-covalent assembly, isoemissive, FMO, NBO.

Introduction

The interaction of free base porphyrins with haloboranes has been the subject of interest today¹⁻³. The reaction of free base *meso*-tetraphenylporphyrin with BF₃.Et₂O yielded a boronated adduct at pyrrolic N centres of the porphyrin with the loss of -NH proton¹. Mohajer *et al.*² demonstrated that BF₃ can form adduct with free base porphyrin which was stabilised by H-bond formation between fluorine of BF₃ and -NH protons of porphyrin.

Covalently bonded dyads to pentads of porphyrins, fullerenes, quinines, spacers and haloboranes have yielded huge information on the energetic and geometrical features of electron and energy transfer processes⁴⁻¹⁰. However, non-covalent interactions are relatively weak and stable supramolecular complexes are only formed when multiple intermolecular interactions cooperate in binding¹¹⁻¹⁴. Supramolecular architectures of porphyrins may be generated by self-assembly¹⁵⁻²⁰ based on non-covalent interaction and molecular recognition.

Here we have reported the chemical physics of non-covalent interaction of (dibenzoylmethanato)borondifluoride (MBDF1) (Fig. 1) and free base *meso*-tetraphenylporphyrin (P), from among three free base tetraphenylporphyrin (P1-P3) moieties involved in non-covalent molecular interaction in methylene chloride medium. We have described spectroscopic investigation supported by DFT based computation of the assembly of supramolecular porphyrin-(dibenzoylmethanato)borondifluoride entities which are formed both in the ground as well as in excited state via hydrogen bonding¹⁵⁻¹⁸ and charge transfer^{19,20}. Mulliken charges, FMO features, NBO indices successfully describe the experimental non-covalent interaction.

Results and discussion

Ground state interactions :

The binding process of the electron rich porphyrin systems (P) to MBDF1 were monitored by visible absorption spectroscopy. A solution of the MBDF1 was

Fig. 1. Structures of the compounds used.

titrated with a stock solution of three tetraphenylporphyrin (P1, P2 and P3) in methylene chloride, separately. For all the three porphyrin systems (P), intensity of maximum absorption of MBDF1 decreased monotonically by adding solutions of P, each giving a set of three isosbestic points, as shown in Fig. 2. Along with reduction of the intensities of MBDF1, absorption maxima of all the porphyrin systems (P) increased monotonically giving rise to

a set of isosbistics at the juncture and were collectively shown in Fig. 2 as in case of P3. There is also red shift of the absorption maxima of MBDF1 by successive addition solutions of P. Table 1 reported the multiple isosbestic points in different regions of the spectra on interaction of P1, P2 and P3 with MBDF1 in methylene chloride. Thus all the three interacting P systems form stable equilibrium with MBDF1 in methylene chloride medium in the

Fig. 2. Absorption isosbestic points appeared due to interaction of P3 with MBDF1 in methylene chloride (1.65×10^{-5} mole/dm³), concentrations of P3 : 0.00, 2.55×10^{-7} , 4.67×10^{-7} , 6.47×10^{-7} , 8.01×10^{-7} , 9.35×10^{-7} , 1.05×10^{-6} , 1.16×10^{-6} , 1.25×10^{-6} and 1.33×10^{-6} mole/dm³.

ground state. The interaction is probably a combined phenomenon between the moieties incorporating electron donor-acceptor, π -stacking and H-bonding effects. The electron rich P systems can donate electrons to the electron deficient MBDF1. The pyrrolic N-H protons of the porphyrins can participate in H-bonding with the F-atoms of MBDF1 which was explored through theoretical computation.

Excited state interaction :

The fluorescence maxima of MBDF1 did not suffer any shift with the increasing concentration of any porphyrin system in the solution, as shown in Fig. 3. Only the fluorescence intensity of MBDF1 diminished monotonically

Fig. 3. Isoemissive point appeared on excitation at 435 nm due to interaction P2 with MBDF1 in methylene chloride (1.65×10^{-5} mole/dm³), concentrations of P2 : 0.00, 2.55×10^{-7} , 4.67×10^{-7} , 6.47×10^{-7} , 8.01×10^{-7} , 9.35×10^{-7} , 1.05×10^{-6} , 1.16×10^{-6} , 1.25×10^{-6} and 1.33×10^{-6} mole/dm³.

with increasing concentration of P, along with the appearance of a new peak at the far wavelength region. This gave rise to an isoemissive point for each of the three tetraphenylporphyrins (P). The appearance of the new peak with increasing concentration of porphyrins (P) in the region of ~ 640 nm particularly indicated the formation of a new weak adduct in methylene chloride medium. For the appearance of isoemissive we could infer the existence of excited state equilibrium. Isoemissives are also listed in Table 1. The emission profile of the fluorophore (MBDF1) in Fig. 3 showed a decrease in fluorescence intensity with increasing concentration of P2. The effect is due to quenching by P2 in which case the emission frequency has not shifted. It appears that the emission process suffers an interaction between the fluorophore and the quencher (P2) which is adequately

Table 1. Isoabsorptive and isoemissive points appeared on interaction of porphyrins with MBDF1. The ground state equilibrium constants and excited state Stern-Volmer quenching constants for the corresponding three complexes

System	Absorption isosbestic point at wavelength (nm)	Ground state equilibrium constant (K) $\times 10^{-6}$	Isoemissive point at wavelength (nm)	Stern-Volmer quenching constant (K_{SV}) $\times 10^{-5}$
P1/MBDF1	433.3, 365.8, 343.6	5.96	649.0	5.4
P2/MBDF1	418.4, 366.7, 333.1	4.51	618.0	4.34
P3/MBDF1	433.4, 364.3, 345.3	6.45	644.6	5.7

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log \{[\text{Complex}]/[\text{MBDF1}]\}$ vs $\log [P1]$ for P1/MBDF1 interacting systems in ground state.

reflected in the appearance of isoemissive point at 618 nm. Here the quenching is most likely to be static in nature because the complex formed in ground state.

Determination of equilibrium constants :

The method proposed by Pocker *et al.*²³ were used to calculate the ground state equilibrium constant by the equation below and values were presented in Fig. 4 and in Table 1.

$$\log \left(\frac{[\text{Complex}]}{[\text{MBDF1}]} \right) = \log K + \log [P]$$

where $([\text{Complex}]/[\text{MBDF1}])$ is the ratio of concentration of the newly formed complex P/MBDF1 and MBDF1, $[P]$ is concentration of porphyrin derivatives and K is the equilibrium constant.

Excited state quenching constant were determined using Stern-Volmer equation²⁴ and the values were presented in Fig. 5 and in Table 1. Table 1 shows that P3 binds with MBDF1 most efficiently among all the three porphyrin systems. Both the ground state and excited state equilibrium constants follow the order : $K_{P3/\text{MBDF1}} > K_{P1/\text{MBDF1}} > K_{P2/\text{MBDF1}}$. The *m*-fluoro substitution in P3 was supposed to form the strongest adduct, as *m*-fluoro group can withdraw electron density due to inductive (-I) effect from the porphyrin core and due to this the

Fig. 5. Stern-Volmer plot of the three interacting systems.

N-H hydrogen atoms become more acidic than unsubstituted porphyrin to interact with the nearby F-atom of MBDF1. The bora-dibenzoylmethanato ring in MBDF1 is planar with the two out-of-plane F-atoms attached to opposite sides of the ring. Moreover the methoxy phenyl rings are in the same plane due to extended conjugation and facilitate better stacked approaching of porphyrin P having two NH hydrogens.

Theoretical analysis :

Structural optimization of all the four interacting systems were done at the MPW1PW91/6-31G level of DFT. In all the cases, orientation of the adducts between donor (P) and the acceptor (MBDF1) moieties were shown in Fig. 6. There is formation of H-bond between B-F fluorine of MBDF1 and N-H protons of porphyrin moiety. In the adduct, the N-H protons go out-of-plane from the plane of porphyrin core towards the F-atom of MBDF1 whereas the -O-(BF₂)-O- group also goes out-of-plane towards the pyrrolic proton (Fig. 5a) possibly due to H-bonding. The H-bond distance of the adducts involving P2 and P3 are very close to each other and is stronger than the adduct involving unsubstituted porphyrin (P1) as shown in Table 2. This is due to the fact that the *m*-fluoro and *o*-chloro groups withdraw electron density (-I effect) from the core of porphyrin and the pyrrolic H-atoms be-

Fig. 6. Orientation of the adducts in (a) P1/MBDF1 (side view), (a') P1/MBDF1 (front view), (b) P2/MBDF1 and (c) P3/MBDF1 interacting systems in DFT optimized ground state geometry, displaying the B-F...H-N distances in Å.

come more acidic, thus facilitates better H-bonding interaction with B-F fluorine of MBDF1. Thus the observed trend of formation constants (K_{SV}) is not in line with the H-bonding interaction. The donor to acceptor charge transfer together with H-bonding is primarily responsible for stability of these complexes. The angle between the two interacting molecules is least in P1/MBDF1 system and is largest in P2/MBDF1 system, which might be a source

of steric effect as was shown in Table 2. The donor acceptor charge transfer interaction is favoured by lower inter-planar angle between the molecules in the adduct. Hence the amount of charge transfer interaction follows the order : P1 > P3 > P2. Both donor-acceptor charge transfer interaction and the H-bonding interaction play vital role in the stability of these complexes. P3/MBDF1 complex is moderately stabilized by both these interactions and has the highest observed formation constant. But, though P2/MBDF1 complex is favoured by H-bonding interaction, this has the lowest value of observed formation constant due to very low charge transfer interaction.

Nucleophilicity index (N)²⁵ of the individual isolated molecules has been calculated and displayed in Table 3. Systems with $N > 3.0$ eV are considered to be the strong nucleophiles. Among the porphyrins the unsubstituted porphyrin is the strongest nucleophile and has greater charge transfer ability. Considering nucleophilicity of the free isolated species the order is P1 > P2 > P3. However, the observed trend P3 > P1 > P2 is possibly due to molecular orientation factor in the adduct.

Charge distribution :

Analysis of the Mulliken charge distribution (Table 3) over the atoms of the donor P and on the respective ad-

Table 2. DFT/MPW1PW91/6-31G optimized ground state geometry of adducts and H-bond indexes

System	Angle between the two molecules	H-bond distance (in Å)		H-bond index	
		N-H ¹	N-H ²	N-H ₁	N-H ₂
P1/MBDF1	8.76°	2.275	2.276	0.0089	0.0088
P2/MBDF1	34.59°	2.188	2.235	0.0115	0.0094
P3/MBDF1	13.34°	2.182	2.217	0.0116	0.0111

Table 3. DFT/MPW1PW91/6-31G calculated ground state descriptors together with Mulliken charges on individual substrates and their complexes

System	Mulliken charges at porphyrin centres			Nucleophilicity index (N)	Dipole moment (D)
	N (with proton)	Pyrrolic proton	N (without proton)		
MBDF1	-	-	-	2.90	6.7673
P1	-0.858	0.440	-0.607	4.31	0.0131
P1/MBDF1	-0.846	0.461	-0.574	-	5.9995
P2	-0.859	0.443	-0.609	4.11	0.0004
P2/MBDF1	-0.848	0.468	-0.582	-	5.3701
P3	-0.855	0.436	-0.605	3.96	1.1695
P3/MBDF1	-0.845	0.466	-0.571	-	6.1202

ducts shows much variation in the electron densities at different centers. The negative charge of the core nitrogen atoms decreases in presence of MBDF1 indicating charge transfer from the porphyrin core and this is further supported by HOMO picture in Fig. 6. Similarly more positive character was gained by the pyrrolic protons of the porphyrin moiety in the presence of MBDF1. This gives evidence for the H-bond formation between P and MBDF1.

HOMO-LUMO interactions :

The intermolecular type of interaction is conveniently interpreted by analyzing the interaction between the frontier HOMO/LUMO orbitals of the donor-acceptor adducts. The HOMO-LUMO interactions between P and

MBDF1 were studied through density functional calculations at the MPW1PW91/6-31G level. Fig. 7 depicted that HOMO orbitals of the complexes lie mainly on P while LUMOs reside on acceptor MBDF1 moiety, mainly. This was justified in the picture of electron donor-acceptor system with the electron rich porphyrin (P) and electron deficient MBDF1. Thus the frontier molecular orbital picture gives a visual description of charge transfer interaction occurring between free base porphyrin P and haloborane MBDF1 along with H-bonding interaction.

Wiberg NBO bond index :

Calculated values of Wiberg NBO bond index are presented in Table 2. Values of H-bond indexes are in well agreement with the calculated H-bond distances of the

Fig. 7. Frontier molecular orbital pictures of all the three interacting systems at HOMO and LUMO electronic stages.

complexes. The reasonable value of H-bond indexes are in support of the existence of weak H-bond in the adducts. P2 and P3 have greater H-bond indexes, indicating stronger H-bonding interaction as compared to P1.

Conclusion

Chemical physics of binding property have been measured experimentally and H-bond indexes were calculated theoretically for the complex adducts. Three factors viz. charge transfer, steric congestion and H-bonding together play effective role in determining the binding ability of (dibenzoylmethanato)borondifluoride (MBDF1) with three different free base tetraphenylporphyrins in both ground and excited electronic states.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Methylene chloride of Merck, India, used as solvent was of HPLC grade. (Dibenzoylmethanato)borondifluoride (MBDF1)²¹ and the three tetraphenylporphyrin systems (P1-P3) used were prepared according to the reported methods²² respectively. The concentration of MBDF1 was taken in the range 10^{-5} M in all the spectral measurements. The concentration of P was of the order of 10^{-6} M.

The absorption (UV-Vis) spectral measurements were performed with a Shimadzu UV 1800 series PC spectrophotometer fitted with an electronic temperature controller unit (TCC-240 A). The steady state fluorescence emission and excitation spectra were recorded with a Hitachi F-7000 spectrofluorometer equipped with a temperature controlled cell holder. Temperature was controlled to within ± 0.1 K by circulating water from a constant temperature bath (Heto Holten, Denmark).

DFT theoretical calculations were carried out using Gaussian 09 (Linux), Gaussian, Inc. (USA), software. MPW1PW91/6-31G functional was used for calculating geometries, Mulliken charges, frontier orbitals, bond indexes for all the free systems and their complexes.

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